

operation. No diverse effect was observed till a 20-fold excess of the reagent and 50% DMF concentration in aqueous phase. Both mole-ratio and slope methods indicated the formation of 1:2 (metal: ligand) complex under the experimental conditions. System was found to obey Beer's law over the range 5–50 μg of copper(II).

The effect of foreign ions on copper(II) determination was studied at 2% tolerance limit. In the estimation of 20 μg copper(II), the following ions did not interfere when present in amounts (μg shown in parenthesis): Ni^{II} (400), Co^{II} (260), Hg^{II} (210), Bi^{III} (120), Mn^{II} (120), Cd^{II} (30), Ag^{I} (210), Cr^{VI} (200), Al^{III} (40). No interference was observed even after 6000 μg each of V^{V} , Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} , but Zn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Pb^{II} interfered seriously. When the determination was made at pH 12.0 more than 6000 μg of Al^{III} was tolerated. Ag^{I} and Hg^{II} were tolerated upto 1200 and 900 μg respectively when 10-fold excess CPSPDTT was used. Among the anions tested, the presence of more than 500-fold excess of nitrate, sulphate, iodide, bromide, fluoride, carbonate, thiocyanate and acetate had no diverse effect. Thiosulphate (270), persulphate (1100), citrate (40) and oxalate (150) were tolerated, but EDTA interfered seriously.

The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were calculated to be $1.08 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.006 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The average of 10 determinations of 20 μg copper(II) in 10 ml of toluene was 19.97 μg with standard deviation of 0.003. The method was applied for synthetic mixture of aluminium alloy having composition: Cu, 4.10; Fe, 0.43; Mn, 0.19; Ni, 1.93; Si, 0.29; Mg, 0.16%. The determination of copper(II) was carried out at pH 12, as aluminium(III) did not interfere at this pH. The mean of three determinations of the amount of copper was found to be 4.07%. The present method was found to be simple, rapid and precise. The total operation for each run required not more than 10–12 min.

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A Rapid Ultraviolet Spectrophotometric Method for Simultaneous Determination of Nitrate and Nitrite in Potable Waters

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NITRITE when correlated with other forms of nitrogen in water can provide an index of organic pollution¹. Also, nitrite reacts with secondary

amines to form nitrosamines, many of which have been reported to be carcinogenic². Nitrate causes a disease in infants called methaemoglobinemia³. Innumerable methods have been reported for the estimation of nitrite⁴ and nitrate⁵ in water. Wetters and Uglum⁶ determined nitrate and nitrite from the same solution by uv spectrophotometry but at different wave-lengths. Nitrate has been reported to absorb at 220 nm and a method for its estimation has been adopted by American Public Health Association⁷. It has been observed that nitrite too similarly absorbs at the same wave-length but this absorption is suppressed by about 90% on treatment with 1.0 N hydrochloric acid and digestion for 5 min. This quantitative nature of suppression has been exploited here to determine nitrate and nitrite simultaneously at the same wave-length in potable waters where the level of interfering elements and organic matters which absorbs in uv region are appreciably low. This method has been successfully applied in the determination of nitrate and nitrite simultaneously in some natural well waters of Shillong city.

Experimental

A Varian 634-S double beam digital spectrophotometer was used.

1.0 N HCl (A.R.) was used. Stock nitrate solution (1 ml = 100 μg $\text{NO}_3 - \text{N}$) of potassium nitrate (A.R.) was prepared in distilled water and standard nitrate solution (1 ml = 10 μg $\text{NO}_3 - \text{N}$) was prepared by proper dilution. Stock nitrite solution (1 ml = 250 μg $\text{NO}_2 - \text{N}$) of sodium nitrite (A.R.) was prepared in distilled water and standard nitrite solution (1 ml = 10 μg $\text{NO}_2 - \text{N}$) was prepared by proper dilution.

Procedure: In step-I, a suitable aliquot containing 0–250 μg of nitrogen (NO_3/NO_2) was diluted to 50 ml and its absorbance for 220 nm against distilled water was measured. In step-II, the same amount of aliquot of the sample was taken and 1.0 N HCl (1.0 ml) was added and digested for 5 min. The solution was cooled to room temperature and made upto 50 ml and its absorbance was measured (220 nm) against distilled water as above. A calibration curve was prepared in the range 0–350 μg N.

Results and Discussion

Both nitrate and nitrite in water samples absorb together at 220 nm. The absorbance obtained from the step-I is due to nitrate and nitrite together. The absorbance obtained from the step-II is due to nitrate and 10% of nitrite.

The suppression of nitrite absorption due to the addition of hydrochloric acid remains constant above 25 μg nitrogen per 50 ml upto a concentration of 250 μg nitrogen. Below this concentration the suppression of nitrite absorption is not constant, therefore nitrite, if present below a concentration of 20 μg nitrogen per 50 ml, can accurately be

NOTES

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF NITRATE AND NITRITE ADDED TO PURE DISTILLED WATER (n=5)

NO ₂ -N μg	NO ₃ -N μg	Absorbance (X) (NO ₃ +NO ₂)	Absorbance (Y) HCl treatment (NO ₃ +NO ₂)	NO ₂ -N found μg	NO ₃ -N found μg
6.0	46.0	0.282	0.263	3.9	47.3
6.0	215.5	1.208	1.185	4.5	214.2
24.0	24.0	0.276	0.148	23.0	23.3
24.0	200.0	1.113	0.986	22.8	199.4
48.0	4.0	0.308	0.042	51.1	2.6
48.0	40.0	0.479	0.235	47.3	38.8
96.0	80.0	0.949	0.462	94.0	81.5
144.0	12.0	0.892	0.174	143.6	20.0
144.0	120.0	1.396	0.698	140.0	124.5
192.0	20.0	1.162	0.219	192.0	21.0
192.0	200.0	2.049	1.081	196.0	195.0
240.0	25.0	1.439	0.248	243.3	23.0

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF NITRATE AND NITRITE IN WELL-WATERS (n=5)

Sample no.	Aliquot ml	NO ₃ -N added μg	NO ₃ -N found μg	Recovery %	NO ₂ -N added μg	NO ₂ -N found μg	Recovery %
S-1	3.0	0.00	47.9 ± 1.10	—	0.00	0.00	—
	3.0	50.00	98.5 ± 1.35	101.2	55.00	53 ± 1.26	96.4
S-2	3.0	0.00	30.0 ± 1.70	—	0.00	0.00	—
	3.0	100.00	131.0 ± 1.16	101.0	110.00	107 ± 1.50	97.3
S-3	5.0	0.00	139.0 ± 1.70	—	0.00	0.00	—
	5.0	25.00	165.5 ± 1.10	106.0	77.00	77.00 ± 1.83	100.0
S-4	3.0	0.00	49.5 ± 1.72	—	0.00	0.00	—
	3.0	200.00	251.0 ± 1.32	100.7	33.00	32.1 ± 1.97	98.2

estimated by the method of standard addition. Similarly, nitrate-nitrogen below 20 μg per 50 ml can not be measured accurately as is evident from Table 1.

Effect of temperature : At room temperature the suppression of absorption due to nitrite is not complete but heating (water-bath) the sample solution containing nitrite in the range 25–250 μg per 50 ml and 1.0 ml of 1.0 N hydrochloric acid at ~100° suppresses the nitrite absorption by 90% while nitrate absorption remains unaffected. To see the effect of varied amount of hydrochloric acid on the suppression of nitrite absorption, different concentrations of HCl were used. A 1 ml of 1 N HCl per 50 ml of final volume was found to be most satisfactory. Different acids were tried but hydrochloric acid was found to be most suitable.

Effect of diverse ions : The effects of various ions and organic matter were investigated. It was found that organic matters, Cr^{VI}, hydroxyl ion, carbonate, detergents seriously interfered. The interferences of other ions (concentration in ppm) which cause less than 5% error in the determination are as follows : Fe^{III} (0.70), Cu^{II} (0.15), Pb^{II} (1.00), Mo^V (0.40), Cr^{VI} (0.20), V^V (0.20), iodide (0.2), thiosulphate (1.00), thiocyanate (1.00) and bromide (3.00).

The reproducibility of this method was checked on 0.5 ppm of NO₂-N for 10 replicate determinations ; the relative standard deviation was 4.0%.

In order to see the efficacy of the proposed method, it was applied on six well-water samples collected from different parts of Shillong city. Nitrate content of each type of water was found high while nitrite content was almost negligible. Results are shown in Table 2.

Conclusion : This method has been successfully applied on the well-water samples for the determination of NO₃ and NO₂ contents. This method may also be applied for standardising commercial grade nitrite for use in analytical works. This method fails if water samples contain organic matter and interfering elements.

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